

Graphitic carbon nitride photocatalysis: the hydroperoxyl radical role revealed by kinetic modelling

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Metal-free graphitic carbon nitride (GCN) is an optical semiconductor with the advantage of in situ H₂O₂ generation parallel to pollutant removal. Many studies showed the capability of GCN materials for simultaneously producing H₂O₂ and high degradation of organic pollutants in waters. Different mechanisms have been proposed for the heterogeneous GCN mediated photocatalytic process. These authors indicated that the

photogenerated electrons are consumed by dissolved oxygen (DO), forming H_2O_2 by the two-electron or one-electron reduction routes. For the last, protons are necessary for H_2O_2 generation. In addition, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ and HO^{\cdot} could be formed. These reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the photogenerated positive hole (h^+) can oxidise organic pollutants.

In this context, an estimation of the participation of the different reactive species has been attempted using radical scavengers, but this methodology has significant drawbacks that influence their application and limit the interpretation of results. Achieving a deep insight into the photocatalytic mechanism of GCN materials might be helpful to its practical application and contribute to the knowledge in radical pathways. However, it is not simple to isolate the role of each chemical species, especially the ROS with lower reactivity, because their scavenging effect involves the removal of other more reactive species. This is the case of HO_2^{\cdot} , whose role in advanced oxidation processes would be hidden by the non-selective and highest reactivity of HO^{\cdot} . In this context, this study reports the principal role of HO_2^{\cdot} in GCN based systems by the first kinetic simulation of this photocatalytic process.

In this article, Kintecus simulation has confirmed to be an effective tool for defining the mechanism of photocatalytic processes. This work provided considerable kinetic data of radical reactions with the GCN material; many of them were estimated for the first time. Multiple combinations of all different degradation pathways identified in the literature were investigated, deducing for the first time that HO_2^{\cdot} , as a secondary radical, is the main species involved in both the primary oxidation of phenol (PhOH) and simultaneous H_2O_2 generation. The oxidation of PhOH by h^+ is positioned as responsible for around 60% of PhOH oxidation, and PhOH reduction by photogenerated e^- was discarded by the simulation. Although the redox potential is more positive than the valence-band top (VBT) of GCN, the reaction between PhOH and holes is necessary for achieving the best fit between the experimental results and the simulation. This was supported by the double-

beam photoacoustic spectroscopy (RDB-PAS) analysis of the energy-resolved distribution of electron traps (ERDT) that found more negative values than the conduction-band bottom (CBB). These energy states could be interpreted as additional band positions near the calculated VBT. So, investigating the ERDT of electron-traps corroborated the thermodynamic feasibility of the proposed reactions. In addition, the established photocatalytic model reveals that the influence of DO has a different effect than that described in classical theories. The avoidance of recombination of the photogenerated charges is favoured by the presence of DO due to the reduction reaction of oxygen in the CB. However, this reaction is not increased by the percentage of DO in water as it had been established until now. The modelling results revealed that the DO amount increases HO_2^\bullet concentration by the reaction between phenoxyl radical and oxygen, increasing the effect of this radical on PhOH degradation. In addition, HO_2^\bullet , oxygen and protons are identified as the products from the slight decrease in H_2O_2 concentration from its reaction with h^+ . This reaction is only favoured when PhOH is completely removed. The simulation concluded a negligible effect of the electrons, $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$, HO^\bullet or HO_2^\bullet in H_2O_2 removal. In sum, we could establish the route for PhOH degradation, portraying the major contributors to its removal and the importance of DO in the system. The simultaneous evolution of H_2O_2 was clarified by combining the reactions taken into account in this system. Carefully planned simulation methods of experimental data can better comprehend the phenomena occurring during pollutant oxidation that we cannot rationalise experimentally.

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